

A New Reagent for Determination of Copper(II) : 2-(α -Pyridyl)thioquinaldinamide

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A new sulphur reagent for copper(II) has been synthesised for its detection and determination. A very simple, rapid and useful spectrophotometric method for trace analysis of copper has been developed and reported in this paper. A blue-violet copper(II) chelate formed over a wide pH range 0.5-6.5. Copper(II) has been determined in presence of VV, MoVr, WVr, UVr, PbIr, FeIII, BiIII, in presence of masking agents. Alloy steel samples have been analysed for trace analysis of copper. A 1 : 3 (M-R) composition of the complex has been determined. The overall stability constant of the chelate is found to be 13.04 (log K) in 50% ethanol-water at $27 \pm 1^\circ$.

THERE are several spectrophotometric methods described by various workers for the determination of copper, but their methods suffer from many disadvantages¹⁻¹³ and interferences.

The synthesis of a new chelating reagent is reported here and it forms a stable complex both in solution and in solid phase. The sulphur reagent is highly stable and can show both the tautomeric forms represented as given below.

2-(α -Pyridyl)thioquinaldinamide Thioureide Thiol

The use of the reagent for sensitive and selective photometric method of determination of copper(II) is described in 50% ethanol. The π -bonding nature of the thiouride group offered high selectivity besides high thermal stability of the complex. *N*-2-Pyridylthioquinaldinamide (IndcoP) is a bright yellow stable crystalline (needle) sulphur compound and highly soluble in organic solvents. The metal has been determined in synthetic mixtures and alloy steels.

Experimental

A spectromom 204 and a Hilger-UVispek spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells were used for absorbance measurements. pH of the solutions was measured with a Elico L1-10 pH meter. Ir spectra (nujol) was taken with a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometers.

Reagents : An accurately weighed quantity of copper sulphate pentahydrate was dissolved in

double-distilled water and standardised by α -benzoinoxime method. A 0.1% reagent in ethanol was used. A 0.1 M hydrochloric acid was used to adjust the pH in the measurements. A 10% triethanolamine hydrochloride was prepared from A.R. quality TEA (R.I. 1.484-'8). All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. A buffer solution of pH 2.7 was obtained utilising 1 M sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid mixture with proper dilution.

The reagent was synthesised¹⁴ following Willgerdot's reaction. The reagent is newly synthesised¹⁴. 2-Aminopyridine (2 mol), quinaldine (1 mol) and sulphur powder (1.5 mol) were mixed and refluxed for 6 h in a 250 ml flask fitted with bulb condenser under controlled temperature (140-150°) at 1 atm pressure over sand-bath. The reaction mixture was kept overnight. The thio-compound was filtered and crystallised using petroleum ether to give a yellow solid. The compound crystallised from ethanol was dried under vacuum (0.1 mg of Hg) for 24 h, 20% (based on quinaldine), $155 \pm 1^\circ$ (Found : C, 72.1; N, 10.30; H, 4.2. C₁₅H₁₁N₃S calcd. C, 72.43; N, 10.55; H, 4.55%), mol. wt. 265.33.

Recommended procedure :

An appropriate amount of copper(II) solution was taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask. To it was added 0.1% reagent (5 ml) followed by ethanol (7.5 ml) and the pH adjusted to 2.9. The solution was diluted with water and mixed thoroughly at room temperature. Reagent blank prepared under similar condition without metal ion showed no absorbance. The absorbance of the blue-violet complex was measured at 50 nm against water blank.

Results

The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Variables studied	Characteristics of copper(II) complex	
	Range studied	Maximum
Absorbance (nm)	400–700	560 (λ_{max})
Effect of pH	0.5–6.5	2.1–3.7
Effect of reagent (0.1%)	0.3–10 ml	3.5–8.5 ml
Beer's law, Ringbom's plot	0.25–15 ppm	Optimum 1–9 ppm
Time	Stable for 24 h at room temperature	
Molar absorptivity at 560 nm	$7.9 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	
Sensitivity, % relative error ^{1a}	0.008 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ of Cu^{II} with 2.7% error	
Composition of the complex	1 : 3 with $1.574 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ metal solution	
Degree of dissociation, stability constant ^{1a}	0.2937 with log K value is 13.04 at $27 \pm 1^\circ$	

Interference studies : The studies on the effect of diverse ions with 2 ppm of copper(II) in the final volume of 25 ml were made following the procedure at pH 2.9. The absorbances were measured at 550 nm and 0.005 was taken as the standard tolerance limit for the system. A 500-fold excess of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Ti^I , Ti^{IV} ; 200-fold excess of Sn^{II} , As^{III} , Sb^{III} , Ce^{IV} , UO_2^{II} ; 10-fold excess of Pb^{II} , Bi^{III} , Mo^{IV} , Hg^{II} , Fe^{III} , Fe^{II} , V^V , Cr^{VI} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} , Os^{VIII} , Re^{VII} have been tolerated. Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ga^{III} , In^{III} , Al^{III} , Ca^{II} , Be^{II} do not interfere. Ag^I , W^{VI} have shown interference. Sulphate, nitrate, phosphate, acetate, borate, fluoride, citrate, tartrate, oxalate, triethanolamine/HCl do not interfere. 10-fold excess of EDTA, iodide, cyanide, thiocyanate and thiourea have been tolerated. 500-fold excess of EDTA in presence of Ca and a large excess of KI in acetic acid medium do not interfere. A 500-fold excess of Fe^{III} has been tolerated with 0.5 g of tartaric, citric or ascorbic acid. The colour is clear blue-violet in acetone medium and ascorbic acid as complexing agent. A 100-fold excess of Hg^{II} with 0.1 g of potassium iodide in acetic acid medium has been tolerated.

Conclusion :

The complex is non-extractable in many solvents with a stable coordinating group (–CS–NH–) bonded to Cu^{II} . From ir spectral studies, the H-bonding is absent in the complex¹⁷. The octahedral complex showed lowering of –CS–NH– band by 60 cm^{-1} . The yellow complex formed by one of the tautomeric forms of the reagent in chloroform has molar absorptivity $8 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The anilide offers rapidity and accuracy required for biological samples. In the present method most of the metal ions do not interfere, and for others the procedure described worked with minimum interferences.

Discussion

Determination of copper in presence of V^V , Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} : To a Cu^{II} solution (0.1 mg) in a 50 ml beaker was added vanadate (10 mg, V), molybdate (20 mg, Mo) and tungstate (5 mg, W) solutions. Then, 0.1 g each of hydroxylamine hydrochloride or ascorbic acid, oxalic acid, and tartaric acid were mixed for reduction and masking, respectively and

slightly warmed and cooled. pH of the mixture was adjusted to 2.9. Then 0.1% reagent (5 ml) was added, cooled and transferred quantitatively into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The volume was made up with 50% ethanol. Similarly, a reagent blank was prepared for absorbance measurement at 560 nm. The complex formed directly in the 25 ml flask. Copper was determined to be $0.099 \pm 0.001 \text{ mg}$ in both the experiments and also in 50% acetone medium where the colour became more clear violet.

Determination of copper in presence of As^V , Sb^{III} , Bi^{III} , Pb^{II} : To a Cu^{II} solution (0.1 mg) in a 50 ml beaker was taken arsenic (50 mg, As), antimony oxide (50 mg, Sb), bismuth (50 mg, Bi) and lead (50 mg, Pb) nitrate solutions. Then 20% aqueous solution (5 ml) of triethanolamine hydrochloride and/or acetic acid were mixed for complexation and masking, and pH was adjusted to 2.9 with acetic acid. The solution was transferred with 0.1% reagent (5 ml) added to it. The volume was made up to the mark with ethanol. Similarly, a solution blank was prepared without adding reagent and used for absorbance measurement at 560 nm. The complex formed directly in the 25 ml flask. Copper was determined to be $0.099 \pm 0.001 \text{ mg}$ in both the experiments.

Determination of copper in alloy steel in presence of Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} : Steel sample (0.5 g) was dissolved in 3 M sulphuric acid (50 ml) and digested on a hot-plate repeating the addition of acid. The solution was then treated with a few drops of concentrated nitric acid for complete digestion. The clear solution obtained was evaporated, and then cooled, diluted with water (50 ml), filtered and washed with dilute acid. The filtrate and washings were cooled and transferred quantitatively into a 100-ml volumetric flask and the volume made upto the mark. A 5-10 ml aliquot portions were taken in several of the determinations with 0.1% reagent (5 ml), and ascorbic acid (0.2 g) being added in a 50 ml beaker and pH was adjusted to 2.9. The solution was transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The volume made upto the mark with ethanol and mixed thoroughly. A blank solution was prepared similarly without adding the reagent and used in the absorbance measurement at 560 nm. Copper was determined and found to be

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0.32, 0.10 and 0.08% Cu with a deviation of $\pm 0.01\%$ (certified : 0.32, 0.10 and 0.08% Cu in BAS steel). The determination of copper in 50% acetone gave a better result and required longer time to develop.

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